

Fig. 1. Buddha Śākyamuni, gilt copper, 7th century, H. 19¾ in. Collection Ben Heller, New York.

On the Antiquity of Nepalese Metalcraft

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I

Until recently most scholars agreed that Nepalese bronze sculpture could not be dated earlier than the thirteenth century.¹ This view was bolstered by the fact that the oldest date on an inscribed Nepalese metal image was the equivalent of A.D. 1467.² Although a dissenting minority of scholars have thought that some images were much older than the thirteenth century, the dating of these works necessarily rested on stylistic evidence about which opinions widely differed. Indeed, certain bronzes like the famed Boston Padmapāṇi have been assigned almost as many conflicting dates as the number of scholars who have studied them. Recently, however, Pratapaditya Pal has shown conclusively by means of three dated bronzes that the Nepalese were not only casting images in bronze but also creating them in repoussé technique by the beginning of the eleventh century.³ Now, however, three more inscribed metal images have come to light which unequivocally thrust back the use of casting and repoussé techniques in Nepal at least another five centuries.

In introducing these three works here, I wish to stress the epigraphic and historical evidence for their date. Stylistically, they are somewhat diverse, and present important evidence for the development of post-Guptan metal sculpture such as the bronze hoards of Nālandā and Kurkihar as well as those from Nāgapattīṇam in South India and Dhaneśvar-kheri in the north. An exploration of this problem, however, must await another occasion.

One of these newly discovered works is a gilt copper image of the Buddha Śākyamuni in the private collection of Ben Heller, New York (Figs. 1–4). Al-

though sometimes thought to be Indian, the bronze has now been identified as Nepalese and included in an exhibition of Nepalese art held at the Asia House Gallery, New York.⁴ That the Buddha is indeed Nepalese is made evident by the dedicatory inscription engraved on three sides of the base, for the script, derived from Gupta India, is that current in Licchavi Nepal. Although undated, the paleographic features of the inscription may be safely assigned to the seventh century, a date which fully harmonizes with the style of the image itself.⁵

The second early image to be assigned to the artisans of Licchavi Nepal is a bronze Buddha in the Cleveland Museum of Art (Fig. 5), a work usually identified as Indian.⁶ Like the preceding image, the Cleveland Buddha is also inscribed and, further, is dated in an unspecified era. Engraved into the surface, the inscription had offered difficulties to scholars not familiar with Nepalese epigraphy: the numbers

Fig. 2. Detail of Fig. 1, right side of inscribed base.

Fig. 3. Detail of Fig. 1, front of inscribed base.

Fig. 4. Detail of Fig. 1, left side of inscribed base.

indicating the date had been particularly difficult, and the reading of parts of the text had been problematic.⁷ Nonetheless, a solution to these problems can be offered here.⁸

That the inscription is a Licchavi one is not in doubt, as determined by the paleography of the script, the date it contains, and the cultural evidence supplied by the four-line text. The name of the convent, Yaṃgval, in which the donor, the nun Paṛisudhamati, resided is a typical pre-Licchavi (proto-Newar or Kirāta) place name in the Kathmandu Valley.⁹ Yaṃbu, for example, was the name of one of the leading settlements which in time were fused together to form the modern Kathmandu. *Gval*, *gvala* (and its variants *gala*, *gla*, *gara*), meaning “place of deity,” is not only an ubiquitous suffix of place names appearing in Licchavi inscriptions—for example, *Māgval*, *Gīgval*, *Tegval*, and *Yūgval*—but

survives in Newar village names (*Satungal*) and in modern Newar neighborhood (*ṭol*) designations (*Yaṅgal*, *Tyāgal*, *Taṅgal*). Moreover, *Gvala* was the ancient name for Deopatan, the settlement surrounding the famous Śaiva shrine, Paśupatinātha, and is still today the preferred name among Newars for Deopatan.

The exact location of Yaṃgval-vihāra and the companion vihāra mentioned in the inscription, Caityakūṭa Jinabandhu, cannot be determined. But the inscription informs us that Yaṃgval-vihāra, and therefore surely Caityakūṭa Jinabandhu, was in Laḍitagrāma, the village of Laḍita. This is almost certainly to be identified as modern Lalitpur (or Patan, its alternate Nepali name), an ancient Licchavi—and indeed, pre-Licchavi—settlement on the left bank of the Bagmati River across from Kathmandu. Although the indigenous name for Patan-Lalitpur

Fig. 5. Buddha Śākyamuni, bronze, A.D. 591, H. 18 in. The Cleveland Museum of Art (Purchase from the J. H. Wade Fund).

was Yala (as it is still known to Newari speakers), it became the Licchavi Yūpagrāma and, finally, in keeping with most other important Kathmandu Valley settlements, it acquired an alternate Sanskrit name. This was Lalita, or frequently, as in the inscription, Laḍita (beautiful, charming), combined with varying suffixes denoting settlements of varying size or importance— *-kramā*, *-brumā*, *-pura*, *-nagara*, *-paṭṭana* (from whence Patan), and *-grāma*.

That the inscription on the Cleveland Buddha originated in the Kathmandu Valley is indicated not only by the use of a typically indigenous name like Yaṃgval in conjunction with Laḍita (Lalita), the Sanskritized name for Yala-Lalitpur-Patan, but by the particular use of the word *piṇḍaka*. This word occurs frequently in Licchavi inscriptions where, rather than its use in India to refer to lump tax assessment, it specifically designates that portion of a crop allocated to a landlord or trust (*goṣṭhī*, *gūṭhī*) rather than to a tenant farmer. Thus the donor stipulated that the proceeds from the yield of this particular part of the crop should be used to provide a feast for certain worthies at a specified place east of the Caityakūṭa Jinabandhu vihāra.

That the inscription is a Licchavi one is also borne out by the era date. Vajracharya reads it as *saṃvat* 513,¹⁰ a date in the Śaka era corresponding to A.D. 591 and eminently compatible with the stylistic considerations of the image. The Śaka era was, of course, employed in Licchavi Nepal through the reign of Śivadeva I (A.D. 590–604), until Aṃśuvarman, his illustrious successor, introduced, or at least gave currency to a new era, the Aṃśuvarman *saṃvat*, which was used in Nepal from about its twenty-ninth year until the late ninth century.

The image reportedly came from the Nepalese Tarai,¹¹ which in the instance of a small, portable statue may not be important evidence concerning its place of origin. However, there can be little reasonable doubt that the Cleveland Buddha was cast in the town of Laḍita (Lalita)-Lalitpur-Patan, a renowned center of metallurgical activity from whose still bustling family workshops so many of the great Nepalese bronzes have emanated. Nonetheless, the superb Cleveland image is somewhat flawed by the surprisingly imperfect alignment of the base.¹² Given the restricted size of even modern Patan, the donor

nun Pariśuddhamati must have dwelt near the foundry from which she commissioned the Buddha image. And her dwelling place was the convent of Yaṃgval, one of the innumerable Patan foundations that existed in Licchavi Nepal and whose remnants still bestow upon Patan its particular cachet.

Thus identified, the Cleveland Buddha provides important testimony for the existence of a well-developed tradition of bronze casting in Nepal as early as the sixth century A.D.

With respect to the Cleveland image it is of interest to note that in one other Patan convent another nun made a similar donation of a Buddha image, but in stone, at almost the same time.¹³ The date of the dedicatory inscription is effaced, but on paleographic evidence the stone sculpture may be assigned to Aṃśuvarman's reign, ca. A.D. 605–621, or shortly thereafter.¹⁴ Unfortunately, the relief is too damaged—in part by villagers using the stone to hone knives and grind clay marbles—to permit useful stylistic comparisons with the contemporary Cleveland bronze.

II

In addition to the two inscribed Nepalese images in New York and Cleveland, there is a third inscribed and dated work which provides incontrovertible evidence for the existence of sophisticated metal sculpture in Licchavi Nepal. This work is a gilt copper sheath with the figure of Viṣṇu seated on Garuḍa done in the repoussé technique. Dated in accordance with A.D. 607, it is installed as the glittering cover of the most prestigious Vaiṣṇava icon in Nepal, the Nārāyaṇa of Cāṅgu hill. So sacred is the icon, however, that neither it nor its decorative sheath have ever been photographed, nor have they been viewed by persons outside the pale of the local faith. We must therefore depend on the accounts of Nepalese scholars who have been able to examine the sheath.¹⁵

The ancient sheath is said to resemble one dated in accordance with A.D. 1004 now in the Zimmerman collection, New York (Figure 6). The latter work is inscribed on its basal portion.¹⁶ The sheath covering the Cāṅgu Nārāyaṇa image bears a similar inscription that informs us: “King Aṃśuvarman having seen that the first golden cover of Lord Nārāyaṇa and Garuḍa had become dilapidated with the passage of

Fig. 6. Garuḍāsana Viṣṇu, gilt copper repoussé sheath, A.D. 1004. Collection Jack Zimmerman, New York.

Fig. 7. Garuḍāsana Viṣṇu, 9th–10th century, stone, h. 32.5 in. Cāngu Nārāyaṇa courtyard, Nepal. Photograph Mary Slusser.

time, for universal well-being had it completely restored according to the old model in the year 31 [A.D. 607] on Sunday the thirteenth day of the bright half of the lunar month of Māgha in the lunar mansion Puṣya.”¹⁷

Nepalese scholars who have seen the sheath in situ in the Cāngu Nārāyaṇa temple describe it as resembling in size and appearance the magnificent stone sculpture of the ninth or tenth century which stands in the temple courtyard (Fig. 7). Although it is prob-

ably stylistically distinct from the original cult image or its gilt cover, the courtyard sculpture essentially duplicates the original. Indeed, it seems that the enshrined icon is the prototype of all subsequent Nepalese works on the Garuḍāsana theme. It is perpetuated, for example, not only by the early courtyard Garuḍāsana and a nearby companion image of probable thirteenth century date, but by a third composition enshrined near Paśupatinātha, Deopatan (Fig. 8). Yet these are but three of many similar Garuḍāsana

Fig. 8. Garuḍāsana Viṣṇu, ca. 10th century, stone, H. 21 in. Deopatan, Nepal. Photograph Mary Slusser.

Viṣṇu images of varying age which are scattered throughout the Valley. Eventually the type became modified to include, as in the Zimmerman plaque and another stone sculpture in Kathmandu,¹⁸ two of Viṣṇu's wives, Lakṣmī and Bhū-devī, seated at his sides. Later, still other variations were introduced.

That the two Buddha images and the Cāṅgu Nārāyaṇa sheath—to say nothing of the many other images tentatively dated on stylistic evidence¹⁹—prove to have such early dates should not cause surprise, however, when one considers the numerous literary and epigraphic references to metalwork in ancient Nepal. The fourteenth-century chronicle, the *Gopālarāja-vamśāvalī*, whose credibility in the cultural realm has recently been amply demonstrated,²⁰ is replete with such references. For example, in about A.D. 400 Vṛsadeva, the great-grandfather of Mānadeva I, offered to Lord Paśupatiṅtha an immense gilt trident, a work of no mean technical accomplishment which still dominates the temple's northern side.²¹ In the seventh century Jīva-, or more properly, Jiṣṇugupta, gave the Hadigaon Satya Nārāyaṇa a golden chain²² and on the eleventh day of every lunar fortnight his son, Viṣṇugupta, established votive images of copper or stone.²³ Śivadeva II circulated gold and silver coins, covered Paśupati's temple with a golden roof, and offered the deity a silver lotus.²⁴ His successor Jayadeva II, as recorded in a stone inscription of A.D. 733, also gave a silver lotus to Paśupati.²⁵ In both instances the silver lotus may have been a cover for the lotus-shaped surround of a *liṅga* such as has the eleventh-century bronze in the Samuel Eilenberg collection.²⁶

From the brush of Wang Hsüan-t'sê, the Chinese envoy who thrice visited the court of Narendradeva in the mid-seventh century, we are also made aware of the Nepalese familiarity with metalcraft. Indeed, considering the brevity of his memoir, the number of references to metal would be quite astonishing did it not so perfectly accord with what we know of Nepalese skills in this field in later times. "All their utensils are made of copper," the ambassador writes, "they have coins of copper which bear on one side a figure of man and on the reverse a horse and a bull. . . . Their king, Nalingtipa [Narendradeva] . . . has in the ears rings of gold and pendants of jade, and a breloc belt ornamented with the figure of the Buddha. . . .

In the middle of the palace there is a tower of seven storeys roofed with copper tiles. . . . At each of the four corners . . . there projects a waterpipe of copper. At the base there are golden dragons which spout forth water. From the summit . . . water is poured through runnels [and streams] like a fountain from the mouth of the golden Makara."²⁷ The seventh-century Chinese pilgrim, Hsüan-tsang, heard at Vaiśālī that Nepal "produced red copper" and that coins of it were used in commerce.²⁸

The custom of offering a gilt cover, or supplementary dress, as it were, to the images of deities is common to India and Nepal. Known in Nepal as *kośa* or *kavaca*, the cover is often given long after the original foundation. For example, according to the testimony of the *Gopālarāja-vamśāvalī*, the great stone bull facing Paśupati's western doorway was established in the mid-fifth century by Dharmadeva, Mānadeva's father, but it was not sheathed in gilt copper until the late thirteenth century.²⁹ Similarly, the Mother Goddess worshiped as Śītalā in Haugalbahāl, Patan, a venerable image of about the fourth century A.D. (Fig. 19) has for ceremonial use a gilt copper *kośa* of seventeenth or eighteenth century date (Fig. 10). The celebrated Aśoka Gaṇeśa in the Kathmandu Darbar Square boasts four latter-day *kośas* which he wears in rotation one every Tuesday, his special day of worship. Similarly, the miniature gilt repoussé *caturmukha liṅga* illustrated by Pal and dated on stylistic considerations to ca. A.D. 800,³⁰ was almost certainly intended to cover a still older stone *liṅga* employed in domestic worship.

Although often far less beautiful than the original images they cover, the gilt metal sheaths are thought to embellish the images and to enrich them, as the literal translation of the word *kośa*, "treasure," makes clear. An eighteenth century inscription concerning the encasing of a Śivaliṅga enshrined at Sulihma-tol, Patan, is instructive in this respect. The donor of the *kośa* informs us that "the stone image of Ratneśvara was black as a cloud. But it glittered like Mt. Sumeru when it was covered with a golden *kośa*."³¹ Gilt copper sheathing, it might be noted, is not confined to icons and *liṅgas* but is often applied to stone votive *caityas* and particularly to the carved wooden doors and window frames of temples. The latter sheathings, however, despite their glitter, are almost universally

Fig. 9. "Śitalā," an unidentified goddess, ca. 4th century, stone, h. 38 in. Haugal-bahāl, Patan, Nepal. Photograph Mary Slusser.

Fig. 10. Gilt copper sheath for the Haugal-bahāl image, 17th–18th century. Photograph Mary Slusser.

inferior to the earlier wood carvings they are meant to enrich.

III

If it was necessary in A.D. 607 for Aṃśuvarman to completely restore the *kavaca* of Cāṅgu Nārāyaṇa because it “had become dilapidated with the passage of time,” we must assume that the predecessor sheath was of venerable age. But how venerable we can only surmise.

We do not know the exact foundation date of the temple of Cāṅgu Nārāyaṇa nor of the consecration of the stone Garuḍāsana image within. The present temple, a Newar style structure, or “pagoda,” and the largest in Nepal, dates only from the eighteenth century. But it replaces a succession of temples which, as its predecessor was destroyed by fire, earthquake, or age, have each in their turn crowned the hill since at least sometime prior to the reign of Mānadeva in the fifth century. Counting only from the late sixteenth century, there have been several major restorations. King Viśvamalla of Bhaktapur is said to have raised a new temple over the ruins of a predecessor which “had fallen to the ground” only to have it in turn damaged by fire.³² Gaṅgārāṇī, the grandmother of the Kathmandu ruler, Pratāpa Malla, again repaired the temple³³ but it soon had to be restored again.³⁴ Within twenty years, however, the temple had been “guttled by fire” and was rebuilt once more.³⁵

However, that a temple already stood on the site prior to Mānadeva’s time is clear. Mānadeva’s Garuḍa-crowned victory pillar, dated A.D. 464, no less than Aṃśuvarman’s gilt *kavaca*, was offered to the preexisting deity.³⁶ This is evident from the text of the pillar inscription referring to the enshrined image. Moreover, that it was a Garuḍāsana Viṣṇu is apparent, for the deity is pictured as soaring aloft on his celestial mount to watch over the affairs of the three worlds.

By exactly how long the Nārāyaṇa of Cāṅgu antedates Mānadeva’s pillar is unknown. The chronicles, early and late, concur in assigning the temple to King Haridattavarman, a Licchavi king for whom there are no extant inscriptions but who appears to be a bona fide historical ancestor of Mānadeva.³⁷ That the chronicles’ attribution may indeed be correct receives

indirect epigraphic support from two inscriptions relating to Icāṅgu Nārāyaṇa. Icāṅgu is one of four culturally related Viṣṇu temples, of which Cāṅgu is one, which the chronicles agree were all simultaneously consecrated by Haridatta.³⁸ Thus, when an inscription of A.D. 1200 at Icāṅgu states that the temple was built by Haridatta, the Icāṅgu inscription by extension also confirms Haridatta’s connection with Cāṅgu Nārāyaṇa.³⁹ Similarly, a mid-seventh century inscription at Kēbalpur village associates certain affairs of the Icāṅgu temple with King Vasurāja, Haridatta’s son.⁴⁰ If Haridatta was indeed the founder of Cāṅgu Nārāyaṇa, the original stone Garuḍāsana Viṣṇu would be dated roughly to the beginning of the fourth century A.D.

Thus dated, the first gilt sheath could have been offered to Garuḍa Nārāyaṇa at any time between the early fourth century and Aṃśuvarman’s donation of A.D. 607. Given the protected location of the image, accessible only to the officiating priests, one would expect, however, that the “passage of time” between the original donation and Aṃśuvarman’s had been considerable. Thus, the first cover would certainly have been given at the latest in the previous century. If it were given almost exactly a century before, it would date from the reign of Mānadeva I, ca. A.D. 464–505, who gave to the deity—or at least had inscribed—the famous Garuḍa pillar which once stood before the temple door.

In any event, from the three inscribed images—two cast and one in repoussé, and two of which are securely dated—we now know on the firm basis of epigraphy that the art of metallurgy flourished in Nepal at least as early as the sixth century A.D. Further, from the technical sophistication of the three images, coupled with the explicit testimony of the inscribed Nārāyaṇa sheath, we can safely deduce that the Nepalese were already master metalsmiths long before that time.

IV

The Cāṅgu Nārāyaṇa gilt metal sheath is of profound interest not only for its early date but also for technical and cultural considerations which still have to be explored. For, in contrast to other Nepalese metal sheaths, the one covering Garuḍa Nārāyaṇa is in two separable parts, one for Viṣṇu’s head and neck,

the other for the remainder of the composition. This makes possible the daily removal of the gilt metal head so that the underlying stone head it presumably conceals can be lustrated. Moreover, these two parts are now of quite different dates, the one seventh century A.D., the other seventeenth. Although there is no question that the inscribed major part of the sheath is Aṃśuvarman's donation, the existing head was offered by King Bhūpāendra Malla of Kathmandu in Nepal Saṃvat 814 (A.D. 1694). Bhūpāendra's gift is not only recorded in an in situ inscription at the temple⁴¹ but is corroborated by a *ṭhyāsaphu* (diary) entry.⁴² Inscription and diary entry agree that Bhūpāendra renewed the gilt head, the *torāṇa* of the temple, and performed an extensive *koṭyāhuti yajña* (burnt offering) which lasted for several days. Moreover, from another diarist we learn that eighteen years previous to Bhūpāendra's donation the head was already dilapidated, a condition probably occasioned by the constant daily handling during worship. Thus: "In N.S. 796 Pauṣa-śukla [A.D. 1676] while performing the daily worship of Garuḍa Nārāyaṇa, when the priest removed the head, the neck and its ornament broke off."⁴³ This particular entry not only clarifies why Bhūpāendra's gift was in order but makes abundantly evident the practice of removing the gilt head during the daily worship. It may also explain why the seemingly well-protected sheath had become so "dilapidated with the passage of time" that King Aṃśuvarman had seen fit to restore it "according to the old model."

The knowledge that the Cāṅgu Nārāyaṇa gilt cover is in two separable parts, essentially a unique instance as far as we now know,⁴⁴ provokes many tantalizing questions. One, of course, is whether Aṃśuvarman's sheath and the earlier one it replaced were similarly in two parts so that the head could be removed, and if so, why was the custom ordained with respect to this image alone? Or was only the upper part of Aṃśuvarman's sheath damaged during one of the many destructive fires and quakes at the temple which thus necessitated such a partial replacement? But if so, why did Bhūpāendra not replace the entire sheath, as would be normal in such circumstances, rather than merely the head? Further, could the underlying stone image also have a removable head, or is it perhaps headless, either by accident or

design? Clearly, these questions will have to be answered by further research, both anthropological and art historical. An examination of the sheath itself would certainly at least clarify whether Aṃśuvarman's donation was created in two parts or one.

Meanwhile, attending such study, we may speculate that the original gilt cover was in two parts. This is suggested by Aṃśuvarman's dedicatory inscription in which the word *kavaca* rather than *kośa* is employed. The latter means "treasure" and normally signifies a metal sheath which entirely covers a *caitya*, *liṅga*, or the visible front part of an image or relief. The word *kavaca*, however, implies armor, specifically a coat of mail, or in general usage, a jacket. The use of the specific term *kavaca*, then, rather than the more general one, *kośa*, seems to imply that Aṃśuvarman did not renew the head but only the lower portion covering the god's torso and his mount Garuḍa. Thus, it is conceivable that the head which fell apart in the priest's hands in A.D. 1676 was actually that given by Aṃśuvarman's unidentified predecessor in the fifth or sixth century. The constant handling of the head during daily worship suggests, however, that this head was more probably a post-Aṃśuvarman replacement—indeed, perhaps one of several—for which we have no record. Moreover, the head quite possibly had already been renewed even prior to Aṃśuvarman's gift since surely, given the daily handling, the original head would by then have been the very part most in need of restoration.

There remains the question of why the Cāṅgu Nārāyaṇa sheath, in an almost unique usage, should have been conceived in two parts. Although a removable head may certainly facilitate the daily lustration of the god, this ritual cannot be the reason, for other deities are not so worshiped. If their underlying image is to be bathed the entire sheath and all other clothing and ornaments are ceremonially removed and, after the bathing, replaced. Thus, it seems that there must have been a very special reason to occasion the two-part sheath of Cāṅgu Nārāyaṇa and the priestly practices associated with it. Indeed, we may surmise that it may have related originally to the legend of the headless Viṣṇu recorded in the *Śatapatha-brāhmaṇa*. Concerned by Viṣṇu's dazzling popularity, the jealous gods arranged to have him beheaded, but later, distraught by the loss of such a

peerless deity, the malefactors besought the *Aśvīnas*, the heavenly physicians, to restore *Viṣṇu* to life.⁴⁵

In Nepal, however, the legend of the headless *Viṣṇu* has assumed a puzzling, if not to say pointless, twist as told in the *Nepāla-mahātmya*, an addition to the *Skanda-purāṇa* of probable medieval date. *Viṣṇu*, it seems, in one of his many battles against evil, beheaded a demon who being also a brahmin thus caused the god to commit one of the five most heinous crimes. Knowing himself to be cursed with like fortune, *Viṣṇu* wandered aimlessly until he arrived at the *Cāṅgu* hill, where this curse was indeed fulfilled by the hermit *Sudarśana*—the name of *Viṣṇu*'s symbolic *cakra*, it may be noted. His crime expiated, but minus a head, *Viṣṇu* declared: “Freed from this curse I shall stay here, Oh *Sudarśana*: Worship me here. Persons who worship me on the twelfth day of the moon or on the day of the full moon, as well as Wednesday, will definitely reach heaven.”⁴⁶

The medieval Nepalese legend, pointless as it seems out of context, almost certainly represents a local attempt to explain the peculiar two-piece image of the famous deity of *Cāṅgu* hill and the *pūjā* (worship) offered it. The meaning of the daily removal of the gilt head seems to have been already lost by the time the legend was recorded, but the custom was perhaps originally a symbolic reenactment of *Viṣṇu*'s decapitation by the jealous gods and subsequent restoration by the *Aśvīnas*.

It is further possible that another legend, intimately associated with King *Mānadeva* I, is related to the *Cāṅgu Nārāyaṇa* image and its peculiar sheath. An unwitting parricide tricked into decapitating his sire, the remorseful *Mānadeva* confided his own head to the one-time *Guṃ-vihāra*, and now hilltop shrine of *Vajrayoginī* near *Sankhu*. As such, in the form of a colossal bronze Buddha head, the penitential royal head is even now worshiped. If, as seems possible, *Mānadeva* was associated with the headless *Viṣṇu* legend by an original gift of the two-part sheath to *Cāṅgu Nārāyaṇa*—or perhaps the first of many restorations—this may be reflected in an extremely garbled state in the parricide legend.

Cāṅgu Nārāyaṇa, it may be recorded, also has an alternate icon in the form of a large silver vessel (*kalāśa*) into whose waters the god's essence is transferred for occasional sorties from the temple. For not

only do the Nepalese toil up the Hill of the Palanquin (*Newari, cāṅgum*) to pay their respects to *Garuḍa Nārāyaṇa*, but he returns the compliment by coming twice a year to Kathmandu. The historical origin of this practice is lost in the mists of time but folk tales abound concerning it. One such tale avers that *Viṣṇu* keeps coming to Kathmandu to announce to the King of Nepal his intention to quit the Valley. But because the populace, cleverly instructed by a king of long ago, places inauspicious symbols along his route, at each descent the deity judiciously returns to his ancient hilltop abode to await a more auspicious day for undertaking the proposed journey.

V

The newly deciphered inscription of *Cāṅgu Nārāyaṇa* is of profound importance not only in the study of Nepalese art but also in the study of Nepalese history. It is the only Licchavi inscription to include the *vāra* (weekday) designation together with the supplementary components demanded for exact calendrical reckoning.⁴⁷ It thus provides the first incontrovertible evidence that the Licchavi year was *kārttikādi* rather than *caitrādi*, i.e., that Licchavi reckoning began with the month of *Kārtika* (ca. October 20) rather than the month of *Caitra* (ca. April 20).⁴⁸ Nepalese scholars have believed this to be so for some time through an analysis of inscriptions. For example, *Nirapekṣa*'s *Cāṅgu Nārāyaṇa* inscription dated Śaka 427 *Kārtika-śukla-trayodaśī* refers to *Mānadeva* as the reigning king.⁴⁹ But in the *Paśupati Sūryaghāt* inscription dated in a different month of the same year, 427 *Āṣāḍha-pratipadā*, *Mānadeva* is referred to as the “late king” (*Mānadevo babhūva*).⁵⁰ Because, of course, *Kārtika* precedes *Āṣāḍha* in *kārttikādi* reckoning there seemed little question that the Śaka era as employed in Licchavi Nepal was *kārttikādi*. Similarly, it appeared through a study of the inscriptions prior to that now known on the *Cāṅgu Nārāyaṇa kavaca*, that *kārttikādi* was the system followed in *Aṃśuvarman* era reckonings. For example, an inscription at *Anantaliṅgeśvara* erected in the reign of *Narendradeva* recommends a list of annual religious obligations.⁵¹ That the list begins with the special worship of *Kārtika-śukla-ekādaśī* seemed to demonstrate clearly that the *Aṃśuvarman* year was

kārttikādi. But with the newly deciphered inscription on the *kavaca* there is no doubt concerning which system they followed. For the Śaka era, then, depending on which month amplifies the year date, the conversion numbers would be +78 or +79 and the Aṃśuvarman era numbers +575 or +576. Thus Licchavi dates no longer need be converted by imprecise round numbers but can be rendered with exact correspondence to the Christian era date. The *kārttikādi* system, it may be noted, was continued in the succeeding era, the Nepal Saṃvat. But when the Śaka era was reinstated in late medieval times it was reckoned then in the *caitrādi* system, as in India, as is also the Vikrama Saṃvat, the official era used in modern Nepal.

The Cāngu Nārāyaṇa gilt sheath inscription also serves to underscore once again the catholicity of worship in Nepal so characteristic of all times including today. Aṃśuvarman was an avowed Śaiva who declared himself to be “favored by the feet of Paśupati,” yet saw no conflict in giving the paramount Vaiṣṇava deity, the Garuḍa Nārāyaṇa of Cāngu hill, a splendid gilt cover as a token of his esteem.

The inscription on the Zimmerman plaque (see Fig. 6), it might be noted, is also of considerable historical significance, for it exactly doubles the known inscriptions for the King Udayadeva in whose reign the *kośa* was offered.

For art historical studies, however, the importance of both repoussé sheathes and the two cast Buddha images is certainly their significant role in dispelling the darkness that has heretofore shrouded the antiquity of Nepalese metalwork. By means of these newly discovered works we now know that rather than beginning in the thirteenth century, metallurgy has for a far longer time gone hand in hand with the other arts for which Nepal is so justly famous.

Notes

1. Pratapaditya Pal, “Three Dated Nepali Bronzes and Their Stylistic Significance,” *Archives of Asian Art*, vol. 25 (1971–1972), pp. 58–59 summarizes these views and draws attention to the prophetic and dissenting opinion of Professor Stella Kramrisch.
2. *Ibid.*, p. 59.
3. *Ibid.*, pp. 58–66.
4. Pratapaditya Pal, *Nepal: Where the Gods Are Young*, New York: The Asia Society, 1975, fig. 1.
5. *Ibid.*, p. 70. Pratapaditya Pal and the Nepalese scholar Gautam-

Appendix: Licchavi Inscriptions on Two Bronze Buddha Images

I. The Heller Buddha Inscription

- 1a. mātāpitṛpurogāṇaṃ
- 1b. satvānāṃ dukkhaśāntaye dhyānadevo
yatirbhaktyā
- 1c. gāṇḍabimbamacīkarat

Translation:

For the removal of sorrow of his mother, father, and other sentient beings, the image of Gaṇḍa [Buddha Śākyamuni] is being consecrated by the devout monk Dhyānadeva.

II. The Cleveland Museum Buddha Inscription

1. ũ deyadharmmoyam laḍitagrāme yaṃgvalvihāre
śā[kya] bhikṣuṇyā
2. pariśuddhamatyā yadattra puṇyam tadbhavatu
sarvvasatvānā-
3. manuttarasarvva jñānāvāptaye / saṃvat
- 4a. 500 10 3 / / caityakūṭa jinabandhuvihārapūrvva-
bhuddeśe
- 4b. piṇḍakena bhojanaṃ karttavaya¹ /
1. Mistake for karttavayam

Translation:

This [image] is the pious gift of the Śākya nun Pariśuddhamati who lives in Yaṃgval convent in Laḍitagrāma. Whatever merit there may be in this [deed], may it lead to the attainment of supreme enlightenment of all sentient beings. Saṃvat 513. A feast should be provided [from the proceeds of] *piṇḍaka* at the locale east of Caityakūṭa Jinabandhu monastery.

Gautamvajra Vajracharya
Los Angeles County Museum of Art

vajra Vajracharya have deciphered the inscription; and with the kind permission of Mr. Heller, Mr. Vajracharya is publishing his reading and translation in an appendix to this paper. I am grateful to both Dr. Pal and Mr. Vajracharya for their assistance in the preparation of this paper.

6. Stanislaw Czuma, “A Gupta Style Bronze Buddha,” *The Bulletin of the Cleveland Museum of Art* (February 1970), pp. 55–67, cover, and figs. 8, 12, 13, and 15.

7. *Ibid.*, p. 61–67.

8. At the request of the Cleveland Museum of Art, the inscription was examined at the Museum in December 1974 by Gautamvajra Vajracharya, whose presence in Cleveland was made possible by a study grant awarded him by the John D. Rockefeller III Fund. Assisted by Pratapaditya Pal, Mr. Vajracharya deciphered the inscription, which is included as an appendix to this paper.

9. More than 80 percent of the place names which appear in Licchavi inscriptions are non-Sanskrit ones adopted from the indigenous occupants of the Kathmandu Valley; see Dhanavajra Vajracharya, "Licchavikālakā itihāsamā kirātakālakā prabhāva [Kirāta influence in the history of the Licchavi period]," *Pūrṇimā*, vol. 5, no. 1 (V.S. 2025 Vaiśākha [1968]), p. 6. See also, D. Vajracharya, "Licchavikālika bastī [Settlements of Licchavi times]," *Pūrṇimā*, vol. 5, no. 2 (V.S. 2025 Śrāvaṇa [1968]), pp. 87–109; Baburam Archarya, "Kirāta nāma [Kirāta names]," *Nepālī*, no. 16 (V.S. 2020 Śrāvaṇa [1963]), pp. 3–31. G. Vajracharya informs me that in the *Blue Annals*, a fifteenth-century Tibetan chronicle, there is mention of a Yaṃgval (or perhaps Yangal) vihāra in Nepal, but I have not been able to verify this.

10. That the initial digit is five may be verified by comparing it with the numbers used in other Licchavi inscriptions. See particularly Dhanavajra Vajracharya, "Licchavikālakā abhilekhamā dekhāparekā saṃvatkā añkako nirṇaya [A solution to the numbers appearing in Licchavi inscriptions]," 2 pts., pt. 2, *Pūrṇimā*, vol. 5, no. 4 (V.S. 2025 Māgha [1969]), pp. 280–281. Other useful sources for Licchavi numbers are D. Vajracharya, "Licchavikālakā abhilekhamā dekhāparekā saṃvatkā añkako nirṇaya," pt. 1, *Pūrṇimā*, vol. 5, no. 3 (V.S. 2025 Kārtika [1968]), pp. 181–189; Naya Raj Pant, "Licchavikālakā abhilekhamā dekhāparekā 55 sammakā saṃvatkā añkako nirṇaya [A solution to the numbers appearing in Licchavi inscriptions up to Saṃvat 55]," *Pūrṇimā*, vol. 2, no. 3 (V.S. 2022 Kārtika [1965]), pp. 1–7; "Licchavikālakā abhilekhamā dekhāparekā 59 sammakā saṃvatkā añkako nirṇaya [A solution to the numbers appearing in Licchavi inscriptions up to Saṃvat 59]" *Pūrṇimā*, vol. 4, no. 2 (V.S. 2024 Śrāvaṇa [1967]), pp. 101–106; "Licchavikālakā abhilekhamā paiekā saṃvatkā añkākā pratilipi [Copies of era numbers found in Licchavi inscriptions]," 2 pts., pt. 1, *Pūrṇimā*, vol. 2, no. 1 (V.S. 2022 Vaiśākha [1966]), pp. 1–9, pt. 2, *Pūrṇimā*, vol. 2, no. 2 (V.S. 2022 Śrāvaṇa [1966]), pp. 1–7; Mahesh Raj Pant, "Licchavikālakā añkaparicaya [An introduction to Licchavi numbers]," *Itihāsa-saṃśodhana*, no. 56 (V.S. 2020 [1964]).

11. Czuma, "A Gupta Style Bronze Buddha," p. 63.

12. Czuma, "A Gupta Style Bronze Buddha," pp. 65–66, discusses the technical aspects of soldering the image to its separately cast base and, apparently, of the head to the trunk. It should be noted, moreover, that the metal analysis of the image reveals slight differences between the composition of the base and the image. Thus, although highly unlikely, as Dr. Czuma grees in correspondence with me, the possibility of soldering an Indian image to a Nepalese base cannot be totally ruled out. Further, as Dr. Czuma points out (p. 64), there is also the possibility, however, remote, that the image may not have been cast in the same place that it was inscribed.

13. Pratapaditya Pal, *The Arts of Nepal*, pt. 1, *Sculpture*, Leiden, 1974, pl. 177, pp. 109–110.

14. Dhanavajra Vajracharya, *Licchavikālakā abhilekha* [Licchavi inscriptions], Kathmandu: Institute of Nepal and Asian Studies, Tribhuvan University, 1973, inscr. 95, pp. 382–383. Dr. Pal errs in ascribing a sixth-century date to the image.

15. Until recently outsiders were forbidden even to enter the courtyard. In Sylvain Lévi's efforts to disinter and take rubbings of the now celebrated Cāṅgu Nārāyaṇa pillar inscription at the turn of the century, the French savant had to direct his Nepalese military escort to these ends from a distant gateway (*Le Népal*, 3 vols., Paris: Ernst Leroux, 1905–1908, vol. 3, pp. 1–2). Similarly,

although a few persons have known for some time that there was an inscription on the Cāṅgu Nārāyaṇa image, even Mr. D. Vajracharya, himself of high-ranking priestly class and a distinguished scholar, had to surmount many difficulties before actually being permitted to study the inscription.

16. Pal, "Three Dated Nepali Bronzes," pp. 58–59.

17. Vajracharya, *Licchavikālakā abhilekha*, inscr. 76, pp. 317–319.

18. Pal, "Three Dated Nepali Bronzes," fig. 4.

19. For example, Stella Kramrisch, *Art of Nepal*, New York: The Asia Society, 1964, figs. 3–9; Pal, *Nepal: Where the Gods Are Young*, figs. 2, 14, 23, 36, 54, 69; "Three Dated Nepali Bronzes," fig. 11 (same as Pal, 54 above); *The Arts of Nepal: Sculpture*, pls. 96, 202, 203, 218; *Buddhist Art in Licchavi Nepal*, Bombay: Mārg Publications, 1974, figs. 40, 78.

20. Mary Shepherd Slusser and Gautamvajra Vajracharya, "Some Nepalese Stone Sculptures: A Reappraisal Within Their Cultural and Historical Context," *Artibus Asiae*, vol. 35, nos. 1–2 (1973), pp. 79–138.

21. *Gopālarāja-vaṃśāvalī*, fol. 21a.

22. *Ibid.*, fol. 21b.

23. *Ibid.*, fol. 22a.

24. *Ibid.*, fol. 22b.

25. D. Vajracharya, *Licchavikālakā abhilekha*, inscr. 148, pp. 548–562, with the date now corrected to Saṃvat 157 over earlier readings.

26. Pal, "Three Dated Nepali Bronzes," fig. 7.

27. Translation from K. P. Jayaswal, "Chronology and History of Nepal 600 B.C. to 880 A.D.," *Journal of Bihar and Orissa Research Society*, vol. 22, pt. 3 (1936), pp. 238–239.

28. Samuel Beal, *Si-yu-ki: Buddhist Records of the Western World*. First edition 1884; reprint Delhi: Oriental Books Reprint Corporation, 1969, p. 80.

29. *Gopālarāja-vaṃśāvalī*, fols. 20b, 27a.

30. Pal, "Three Dated Nepali Bronzes," fig. 11, pp. 63–64.

31. The unpublished in situ inscription is in Newari and was translated by Gautamvajra Vajracharya, to whom thanks are gratefully given.

32. D. R. Regmi, *Medieval Nepal*, 4 pts., Calcutta, Patna, 1965–1966, pt. 1, p. 564.

33. Daniel Wright, *History of Nepal*, 3rd ed., Calcutta, 1966, p. 143. At least Gaṅgārāṇī is the accepted name for Pratāpa Mallā's grandmother, although an unpublished *thyāsaphu* suggests that this may not be so.

34. Regmi, *Medieval Nepal*, pt. 2, pp. 148–149.

35. *Ibid.*, p. 877.

36. D. Vajracharya, *Licchavikālakā abhilekha*, inscr. 2, pp. 9–30.

37. *Gopālarāja-vaṃśāvalī*, fol. 19b; D. Vajracharya, *Licchavikālakā abhilekha*, pp. 318–319, 416–417.

38. *Gopālarāja-vaṃśāvalī*, fol. 19b.

39. "Icāṅguko abhilekha [The Icāṅgu inscription]," *Abhilekha-saṃgraha*, pt. 9 (V.S. 2020 Vaiśākha [1963]), pp. 26–27.

40. D. Vajracharya, *Licchavikālakā abhilekha*, inscr. 109 and commentaries pp. 318, 418.

41. *Saṃskṛta-sandēśa*, vol. 1, no. 6 (V.S. 2010 Āśvina [September 1953]), pp. 34–37. The fact that the gilt head postdates the body was brought to my attention by G. Vajracharya, who has demonstrated once again his unfailing cooperation respecting our parallel researches into the cultural history of the Kathmandu Valley.

42. Regmi, *Medieval Nepal*, pt. 3, app. III, p. 37.

43. Gautamvajra Vajracharya, "Aprakāśita thyāsaphu [An unpublished diary]," pt. 1, *Pūrṇimā*, vol. 3, no. 3 (V.S. 2023 Māgha [January 1967]), p. 25.

44. Mr. G. Vajracharya informs me by letter that the Tilmādhava Viṣṇu of Bhaktapur, an early Licchavi stone sculpture, also has a two-piece metal sheath with a removable head. The sheath is of

recent date, however, and very likely was modeled after the famous Cāṅgu Viṣṇu cover. In any event, it seems to be the only other known example of a two-piece sheath.

45. T.A. Gopinatha Rao, *Elements of Hindu Iconography*, 2 vols., Madras, 1914, vol. 1, p. 75.

46. *Nepāla-mahātmya*, ch. 2, vv. 1–69.

47. Curiously, what is now taken to be the last known Licchavi document, a manuscript dated 301, also includes the *vāra* in the date. However, the era is unspecified and has been variously identified. Although it is now conceded to be Aṃśuvarman's, hence A.D. 877, the disagreement about it has invalidated the manuscript date as proof of the system of Licchavi reckoning (D. Vajracharya, *Licchavikālakā abhilekha*, inscr. 190, p. 599).

48. Shankarman Rajvamshi, *Licchavisamvatko niṣkarṣa* [Clarification of the Licchavi era], Kathmandu (V.S. 2030 [1973]), pp. 5–16.

49. D. Vajracharya, *Licchavikālakā abhilekha*, inscr. 19, pp. 79–81.

50. *Ibid.*, inscr. 20, pp. 82–87.

51. *Ibid.*, inscr. 129, pp. 485–489. Only the first digit, an eight, may be read, thus dating the inscription between 80 and 89 (A.D. 656–665), a time well within Narendradeva's reign. This particular

inscription is of more than passing interest because among other things it provides a clue to the identity of the fourth Viṣṇu temple consecrated by King Haridattavarman, the other three being Cāṅgu, Icāṅgu, and Śikhara Nārāyaṇa. The fourth temple was apparently located in the once bustling settlement of Hamaṣagṛhadraṅga on the south side of the Valley, a site which has now reverted to paddy fields. The Nārāyaṇa was known as Lokapālasvāmin and the celebration of his day of consecration, according to the inscription, fell on Kārtika-śukla-duadaśī, the very day the important Four Nārāyaṇa-jātrā is now observed. This *jātrā* entails a visit, traditionally on foot, to all four deities in a single day, a circuit of about 44 miles. Pilgrims have no idea, however, that the fourth Nārāyaṇa, usually considered to be Viśāṅkhu Nārāyaṇa, is actually a somewhat recent substitution for King Haridatta's ancient foundation at Hamaṣagṛhadraṅga. Indeed, it would seem that Viśāṅkhu Nārāyaṇa has displaced Bhuteśvara Gaṇeśa, the deity who appears to have been the occupant of this curious grotto shrine at least at the time of the redaction of the *Nepāla-mahātmya*, perhaps about the 15th century.